

Risk Mitigation of Volunteer Involvement Project during Pandemic in Non-Profit Organizations with 4Ts (Tolerate, Treat, Transfer and Terminate)

Muhammad Mahmudi¹, Sari Viciawati Machdum²

^{1,2}*Social Welfare Department, Faculty of Social and Political Science, University of Indonesia, Indonesia*

ABSTRACT: Covid-19 pandemic has created uncertainty and poses risks for non-profits. This requires the non-profit organizations to adapt, especially how to protect volunteers who involved in projects during the pandemic. It requires an adequate risk management, to ensure that the project is more successfully delivered on time, within budget and to specification. This article discusses how risk mitigation measures as part of risk management flow in a project management that involves volunteers during pandemic at the non-profit organization, GPF Indonesia for the "Peace Circle Project" which was presented in Surabaya in the period of July 2021 to February 2022. This is qualitative research involving stakeholders related to the project as informants who selected through purposive sampling. The results of this study indicate that GPF Indonesia has carried out several mitigation measures during the project based on the priority actions obtained from the calculation of the risk score, considering likelihood of the risk and magnitude of harm. GPF Indonesia carries out 4 main mitigation measures in the project, (1) reduce likelihood of risk, (2) minimizing harm, (3) transfer liability, and (4) communicating risk. These risk mitigation measures can be categorized into 4 hazard responses, tolerate, treat, transfer, and terminate.

KEYWORDS – Risk Management; Volunteer; Risk Mitigation, Nonprofit Organization

I. INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 has dramatically affected the personal and professional lives of the global community with new work habits and working from home [1]. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the involvement of non-profit human service organizations increased in accordance with the increasing of public need for services and programs for handling and recovering Covid-19. The increasing need and role of humanitarian service organizations must be balanced with institutional adaptation to ensure continuity of services to meet community needs.

However, in their efforts to adapt to the new normal during or post-pandemic, humanitarian service organizations are facing uncertainty conditions, such as case fluctuations, policy changes, economic and social impacts as well as changes in people's social life patterns. This uncertainty creates risks that can affect the organization in carrying out its mandate and providing services to the community. The uncertainty that exists can cause risks that can affect 4 categories of assets in the organization, people, property, income, and reputation [2].

One of the risks that must be controlled in risk management mechanisms in humanitarian service organizations is human. In practice, humans are raw materials in a service organization, especially those involving front-line workers, have a very important and crucial role because they deal with clients [3]. Volunteers are no exception, are also important assets and special characteristics of non-profit organizations [4].

The existence of uncertainty due to external conditions of the organization, such as in crisis conditions such as the previous Covid-19 pandemic, will greatly affect staff and volunteers in non-profit organizations with exposure of the risks. In situations such as a pandemic, there is a risk for workers, children, and their families to catch the virus from the process of providing services. Volunteers may also experience concerns about an increased risk of infection in their family members at home. According to volunteer involvement, risks arise

from three broad directions: from the coordination of volunteer involvement; from the work itself; and from volunteer behavior [5].

Facing the circumstances that put staffs and volunteers at the risky situation, it requires proper and good risk management is needed to provide protection for them. Organization such as Global Peace Foundation Indonesia that employ volunteers have a responsibility as a party responsible for volunteers, the responsibility of the institution when a volunteer is injured while carrying out their duties and meanwhile volunteers are also responsible for providing good performance actions according to their duties. These three main things underlie effective risk management [6].

Global Peace Foundation Indonesia is a non-profit organization whose vision is to promote the values of tolerance and peace among Indonesian youth. Since 2010, GPF Indonesia works promoting peace to young people through several peace education program in all over Indonesia. Unfortunately, GPF Indonesia's programs must be stopped in 2020 because of pandemic and start re-running in-person education programs for youth in mid-2021. The first post pandemic project called "*Peace Circle Project*" was conducted in Surabaya, Indonesia, supported by overseas donor. This project consists of 6 program such as, peace camp, peace builder mentoring class, worship houses visit, government visit, family empowerment program, and community peace education.

In the conditions that are still uncertain, the organization must carry out the project with series of risk management stages to protect volunteers who were involved. By undertaking adequate risk management in the intended change, the organization should be able to ensure that the project is more successfully delivered on time, within budget and to specification. Achieving the risk management in the project or program management requires that projects are adequately managed and that the correct project or priorities have been selected by the organization [7].

Previous research indicates there are no discussion about implementation of risk management of volunteer involvement in a project during the Covid-19 pandemic [8] [9] [10]. In pandemic situation, there is an interesting context to study regarding how non-profit organizations respond, with an action to mitigate the risks that occur, especially risk control for institutions that involve volunteers to achieve deliverability of the project. Therefore, this article will discuss about risk mitigation efforts that are part of the risk management stages carried out by the Global Peace Foundation Indonesia related to projects involving volunteers during the covid-19 pandemic using 4Ts (Tolerate, Treat, Transfer, and Terminate).

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses qualitative approach to understand and explore social problems or phenomena. According to Creswell "Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem" [11]. The qualitative approach seeks to see through the informant's point of view and capture stories about the implementation of risk management of volunteer involvement in Global Peace Foundation Indonesia. This research is a case study which examines a limited system within a certain period through detailed and in-depth data collection through various sources of information [11].

This article is based on research conducted in August-October 2022. It examines two kinds of data, primary and secondary data. Primary data is obtained based on the results of observations and interviews with informants. In-depth interviews were not limited to face-to-face interviews; this study also conducted online interviews due to the limited situation caused by the Covid 19 pandemic. Informants in this study were selected through purposive sampling. There are 10 informants in the research, including General Manager, Program Coordinator, and Volunteers of Global Peace Foundation Indonesia. Secondary data is also obtained based on the results of document studies such as organizational reports, standard operating procedures, project manual, social media, and literature studies which could help to understand the risk management of volunteer involvement in HSO.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Risk Management Activities

The risk management process can be defined as a systematic and planned activities including identifying the context, creating a profile of the organization in risk management, and setting risk management objectives, risk assessment, identifying and determining risk priorities, making, and communicating the right decisions, implementation and monitoring and adjustment [12].

The risk management of Peace Projects which involve volunteer in Surabaya carried out by Global Peace Foundation Indonesia has started since the development of the proposal began in January 2021. There are four main steps of the risk management model include: identify risks; sort and prioritize risks; develop and implement risk control measures; and review [5]. The first stage is risk identification which is carried out through several activities such as conducting interviews to all departments to get concerns, conducting brainstorming and internal discussions, conducting simulations and compiling risk breakdowns. The results of the risk identification in this project obtained 3 main categories of risk, health, and safety risk (covid-19 infection, fatigue, car/motorbike accident), fund management risk (fraud, misuse of budget) and activity risk (rejection from beneficiaries, miscommunication). All risks are recorded in the risk table.

The next stage carried out by organization in risk management is sorting and prioritizing risk. In doing this, the risk list is scored by looking at the likelihood of the risk. The likelihood of the risk of being screened is based on the probability, and categorized as low, medium, or high, indeed, this will be different from each volunteer job description. Meanwhile, the impact that may arise from these risks is also scored, whether low, medium, or severe. The results of the scoring will be combined to determine the risk priorities that will determine the mitigation efforts to be carried out. GPF Indonesia then prepares a series of contingency plans and risk mitigation efforts that will be implemented during the project.

3.2. Risk Mitigation

Reduce Likelihood of the Risk

According to the 3 risk categories that have been identified in the previous stage, health and safety risks are the main risk of volunteer work in the project. The Covid-19 infection is the priority to mitigate, it could be from interactions among volunteers, volunteers with participants and partners. One of the mitigation measures made by the organization in reducing the possibility of risk is to stop some activities. The social campaign activities that will be carried out in July 2021, was canceled because the activity requires volunteers to go directly to public areas to provide education to the public. In addition to the pandemic and quarantine conditions which are still at the strictest level, permits are also not obtained due to these conditions.

Another effort to reduce the possibility of risk occurring is to change the method of activity. The possibility to Covid-19 exposure will be higher if the intensity of participants meeting is high, so one of the efforts made is to change the method of activity. In some sub-activities such as mentoring classes are held online which should be held every week. This reduces any possible exposure. In addition, there are several activities that have been postponed by changing the schedule due to the high number of Covid-19 cases and wait until Covid-19 case getting better.

Minimizing Harm

If the activity cannot be stopped, the method is changed or the schedule is changed, so that the activity can continue, the organization also makes efforts to reduce the impact of risks that may arise. Activities that have been running require several standards and procedures to reduce impacts, including how to manage volunteers at all stages of the project. At the initial stage, volunteers who join were required to have a complete vaccination certificate to minimize the severity of the impact of exposure to Covid-19. Of all the 6 volunteers in this project, had received the vaccine before recruited. Meanwhile, all parties involved in the project such as participants, as well as resource persons who attend must have the vaccine certificate, for complete protection. PS as the volunteer coordinator who did the recruitment confirmed this.

In addition, exposure to the Covid-19 virus at the activity venue can be minimized by providing health hygiene and sanitation facilities for all people involved, including volunteers, participants, and partners, such as providing hand sanitizer, face masks, water bottles, and do swab antigens regularly, before and after programs, as well as every two weeks for volunteers. To minimize the impact, the venue must fulfill the standard

requirements where it must be CHSE (Cleanliness, Health, Safety, Environment Sustainability) certified and have been recommended by the government. GPF Indonesia also cooperates with the Covid-19 Task Force of Surabaya City to standardize the venues, meals, procedures, and all program flows in the project. The task force did surveys, checking and monitoring during the project.

Transfer Liability

GPF Indonesia registers all volunteers to health insurance in implementing the project. This is intended, if the worst case happened with severe impact, the responsibility can be transferred to parties who can provide guarantees such as insurance companies. So that the financial losses caused by the accident or health issue, can be reduced.

Communicate the Risks

All prepared mitigation efforts are meaningless if all volunteers do not have the risk awareness. Therefore, communicating risks is important. GPF Indonesia through the Program Coordinator conducts briefings, training, regular meetings for updating, monitoring, and compiles a guidebook containing all program details including risks, and mitigation efforts so that volunteers can understand and implement them. KH as the program coordinator said that weekly meetings were held to monitor the progress of the project and keep communicating the risks and mitigation efforts to volunteers. Activities in communicating the risks also part of minimizing harm.

3.3. Mitigation Measures according to 4Ts (Tolerate, Treat, Transfer and Terminate)

Risk mitigation measures are form of hazard response carried out by the organization to protect volunteers during the project. Based on the results of risk likelihood scoring and the magnitude of harm on the 3 risk categories that may occur in the involvement of volunteers in the Peace Project, combinations of the two were obtained. In the risk management table prepared by GPF Indonesia for the project, the list of risks was grouped into 4 categories, where group 1 is the most urgent and a priority (likelihood of high-magnitude of harm severe), group 2 (likelihood of medium/high-magnitude of harm). medium/severe), group 3 (medium-impact low likelihood, medium low-impact likelihood, severe low-impact likelihood), and 4th group (low-impact low likelihood). There are 4 categories of action, regarding on table of priority: 1st priority needs urgent action, 2nd priority needs as soon as possible action, 3rd priority needs work through when time permits, and 4th priority is not urgent [5].

After having identified the priority significant risks, the organization then needs to review the controls in place and decide whether further actions are required. The 4T is part of the risk management process in relation to the management of hazard risks. It is the options presented for risk response of hazard management, which are: tolerate, treat, transfer and terminate [7]. The following is the categorization of mitigation efforts carried out by the Global Peace Foundation Indonesia based on the 4T hazard response:

Tolerate: Mitigation efforts that can be grouped into this category are mitigation efforts for the risk of miscommunication, reporting errors, incomplete program documentation and archives where these risks have a low-likelihood/low-impact risk. So, the exposure may be tolerable without any further action being taken. Even if it is not tolerable, the ability to do anything about some risks may be limited, or the cost of taking any action may be disproportionate to the potential benefit gained.

Treat: Mitigation measures in the Peace Project that fall into this category include minimizing harm, such as requiring volunteers who involved to be vaccinated in the recruitment process, conducting routine antigen swabs for volunteers, locations must be CHSE and government standards, also provide personal protection facilities. This hazard response is addressed for high-likelihood/low-impact risks. The purpose of treatment is that, whilst continuing within the organization with the activity giving rise to the risk, action (control) is taken to constrain the risk to an acceptable level [7].

In addition, risk communication efforts such as training, briefings, monitoring of volunteers are part of the effort to minimize harm which can be categorized as a hazard response treat. The risks faced by volunteers can be mitigated by registration, safety briefings, completing liability forms, and proper supervision and training. It is also necessary to integrate risk management policies, procedures, protocols and practices in a program with specific attention to the selection and recruitment of volunteers, especially at risk youth groups and the

importance of training volunteers and increasing self-awareness of the risks faced by volunteers [9] [13] [14] [15] [16].

Transfer: Mitigation measure that fall into the hazard response category are providing volunteer health insurance. It is the dominant response for high-impact/low-likelihood risks. This might be done by conventional insurance, or it might be done by paying a third party to take the risk in another way. This option is particularly good for mitigating financial risks or risks to assets [7].

Terminate: Mitigation measures in this category include stopping activities, changing activity methods and delaying activity schedules. It is the dominant response for high-impact/high-likelihood risks. Some risks will only be treatable, or containable to acceptable levels, by terminating the activity [7]. When a risk is both of high likelihood and high potential impact, the organization will wish to terminate or eliminate the risk. Certain risks are best controlled by simply stopping, or ceasing involvement in, the risk-producing activity. This may sound like a radical solution, but it need not mean cancelling the service, withdrawing volunteers, or closing the organization's doors. Stopping the activity might mean terminating single action or function in a larger service area or administrative function [5].

IV. CONCLUSION

Risk management is a series of procedures used to identify risks, carry out risk assessments and priorities, carry out mitigation and control efforts as well as review. Risk management efforts in projects are associated with the implementation of tactics designed to achieve the strategy. GPF Indonesia implements 4 mitigation efforts in projects carried out during the pandemic, there are reducing likelihood of risk, minimizing harm, transfer liability, and communicating risk.

The risk mitigation measures in the Peace Circle Project can be categorized into 4 hazard responses, tolerate, treat, transfer, and terminate. Tolerate response is taken when the risk is tolerable as simple as miscommunication, mis-reporting and other insignificant risk. Treat is taken when the organization need to continue the project with the activity that giving rise to the risk, to constrain the risk to an acceptable level, such as requiring volunteers who involved to be vaccinated in the recruitment process, conducting routine antigen swabs for volunteers, venues must be CHSE and government standards, also provide personal protection facilities. Transfer is an option when risk is high-impact/low-likelihood by providing health insurance which is particularly good for mitigating financial risks or losses. In the other hand, there are certain risks are best controlled by simply stopping the activities, which categorize in terminate.

It concluded that GPF Indonesia had implemented several risk mitigation measures during the Peace Circle Project. The benefits of good risk management within projects are that the project is more likely to be delivered on time, to budget and at the required quality. Risk management activities that GPF Indonesia assist the delivery of the project and, at the same time, help manage a situation when an outcome is different from what was expected as the project progresses and protect the volunteer who are involved in the project as well.

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